

Matching surface treatments to display environments for industrial objects

Yvonne Shashoua, Torben Holst and Henning Matthiesen

Department of Conservation

National Museum of Denmark

Display outdoors

■ **no protection** from variations in temperature, moisture, ultraviolet radiation, salts, pollutants

Display outdoors with shelter

■ **partial protection** from variations in temperature, moisture, pollutants

Display indoors

■ **protection** from variations in temperature, moisture, pollutants, though levels may still be unsuitable

1. Outdoor display

Evans Silver Factory , Birmingham 1881-2008, presently owned by English Heritage

Phase 1 repair building exterior including re-roofing

Phase 2 develop building and contents

Objects requiring conservation: **15,000 dies, tools and presses to produce silver badges, platters etc. Steel cut faces of dies to be preserved**

2. Outdoor display with shelter

Open Air Museum, north of Copenhagen

86 acres of land

50 farms, mills and houses moved from original sites dating from 1650-1950

Objects requiring conservation: **woodworking tools, farm tools some with fabrication marks**

3. Indoor display

Brede Works, north of Copenhagen-Denmark's largest textile factory between 1800s and 1960s

Opened as a museum relating the story of the factory and the industrial revolution in Denmark in 2008

Museum is open April to October and has partial environmental control using low energy systems that control relative humidity

Objects requiring conservation: **machines, transport**

Purpose of research: find the best conservation *surface treatments* to protect iron-containing objects placed outdoors or in partially controlled environments

Specifications for surface treatments:

- protect metal without maintenance for at least 3 years
- allow original function or significance
- reversible or retreatable
- commercially available
- user and environmentally friendly

Literature search:
surface treatments
since 2000

Literature search:
testing methods
since 2000

apply treatments to model substrates
expose to accelerated saltspray and real time
Danish weather
evaluate appearance, adhesion, hardness,
oxygen uptake and electrochemical
impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

apply best performers to pilot objects

monitor performance in-situ

18 surface treatments selected

surface treatment	major components
Corroheat 4010	wax + corrosion inhibitor + solvent
Cosmoloid H80	microcrystalline waxes + hydrocarbon solvents
Dinitrol Car 4941	wax + corrosion inhibitor + solvent
Frigilene	cellulose nitrate + acetone
Incralac	acrylic + corrosion inhibitor + anti.oxidant + solvent
LPS3	wax + corrosion inhibitor + solvent
Paraloid B72	acrylic + acetone
Paraloid B72 with 1% perfluorodecyl iodide	acrylic + flow additive + acetone
Poligen ES91009	wax + surfactant + water
Renaissance wax	Cosmoloid H80+polyethylene wax + solvent
Rustilo 2000	wax + corrosion inhibitor
Rustilo 3000	bitumen + wax + corrosion inhibitor
Ship-2-Shore Industrial	unknown+ water
SP400	wax + corrosion inhibitor
Tectyl 506 rust preventative	wax + corrosion inhibitor
Tectyl Glashelder/Klar acrylic spray	acrylic + corrosion inhibitor + solvent
Tromm III	mixture of waxes + solvent
Vp CI-386 acrylic primer/topcoat	acrylic + corrosion inhibitor + water

Factors which prevent inter-research comparison of coatings:

variation in dry-film thickness ie. apply as manufacturer recommends

solution: all coatings applied at 25 micron dry film. They have already been shown to be effective at slowing corrosion

non-standard testing techniques

solution: BS or ASTM standards where possible

non-standard reference coatings

solution: no reference coatings- equal comparison

Surface treatments were applied to model Q-panels by brush to produce 25microns dry film thickness

Adhesion tests

Renaissance
wax

Poligen ES91009
100% adheres

Paraloid B72
85% adheres

LPS3
42% adheres

Chemical Evaluation of Coatings

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

indicates resistance of surface to corrosion

Oxygen consumption

yields a corrosion rate of iron

Oxygen consumption

Concept: the decrease in oxygen concentration is measured in an enclosed air volume at the metal surface

Oxygen consumption

- Petri dishes attached to panel with epoxy
- small amount of 0.03 M NaCl added
- oxygen concentration measured regularly

Real time outdoors exposure

Visual examination of panels once a week for 1 year

Appearance of panels before (left) and after 1 year of real time exposure

Surface treatment	Adhesion to Q-panel (% of coating remaining on panel) new/after 12 months in Danish weather	Percentage surface covered by corrosion after 504 hours salt spray test (%)	Visible changes after exposure to Danish weather for 12 months	Rate of corrosion by oxygen consumption after 70 days ($\mu\text{m year}^{-1}$)
None (bare panel)		100	corroded	130
Corroheat 4010	97/40	0	very discoloured	2.7
Cosmoloid H80	85/90	0	corrosion at edges	<0.1
Dinitrol Car/4941	100/50	0	loss of gloss. two rust spots	0.7
Frigilene	100/95	50	evenly corroded	0.1
Incralac	90/90	8	spots of corrosion	<0.1
LPS3	40/100	0	darkened	0.1
Paraloid B72	86/40	8	unevenly corroded	0.2
Paraloid B72 with 1% perfluorodecyl iodide (PI)	95/40	50	unevenly corroded	0.4
Poligen ES91009	100/100	50	discrete spots of corrosion	16.6
Renaissance wax	98/100	50	corroded	1.9
Rustilo 2000	100/100	8	evenly corroded	-
Rustilo 3000	100/100	1	loss of gloss	0.4
Ship-2-shore Industrial	liquid-unable to measure adhesion	50	very corroded	1.9
SP400	95/95	0	uneven appearance	0.2
Tectyl 506 rust preventative	100/100	0.5	discoloured	1.5
Tectyl Glashelder/Klar spray	100/100	50	30% surface corroded or discoloured	1.5
Tromm III	99/85	50	50% spots of corrosion	3.5
VpCI-386 acrylic primer/topcoat	100/100	1	20% spots of corrosion	0.1

surface treatment	major components
Cosmoloid H80	microcrystalline waxes + hydrocarbon solvents
Dinitrol Car 4941 (black)	wax + corrosion inhibitor + solvent
LPS3 (aerosol spray)	wax + corrosion inhibitor + solvent
Rustilo 3000 (black)	bitumen + wax + corrosion inhibitor
SP400	wax + corrosion inhibitor
Vp CI-386 acrylic primer/topcoat	acrylic + corrosion inhibitor + water

1. Outdoor display

Specifications for coating:

- ✓ protects against unstable temperature, humidity levels, salts and particles
- ✓ allows retention of original appearance as far as possible
- ✓ in-situ application eg low health and safety requirement
- ✓ application by dipping or brushing

Cosmoloid H80 ***

- ✓ high weathering resistance
- ✓ high UV resistance
- ✓ low gloss and transparent
- ✓ can be applied without solvent

VPCI-386

- ✓ high weathering resistance
- ❖ poor salt resistance
- ✓ transparent and low gloss
- ✓ water-based

SP400

- ❖ medium weathering resistance
- ❖ poor UV resistance
- ✓ low gloss and transparent
- ❖ requires solvent

2. Outdoor display with shelter

Specifications for coating:

✓ protects against unstable temperature, humidity levels, salts and particles

✓ allows retention of original appearance as far as possible

Alkyd paint with graphite in topcoat

- ✓ resisted corrosion for ca. 10 years
- ✓ resembles new iron
- ❖ difficult to remove

Rustilo 2000

- ✓ marked with thumbnail
- ❖ poor resistance to ultraviolet light (experience showed otherwise)

VPCI-386 ***

- ✓ high weathering resistance
- ❖ poor salt resistance
- ✓ transparent and low gloss
- ✓ readily removable

3. Indoor display

Specifications for coating:

- ✓ allows retention of original appearance as far as possible
- ✓ protects against unstable temperature, humidity levels and unwanted handling

Surface treatment	Adhesion to Q-panel (% of coating remaining on panel) new/after 12 months in Danish weather	Percentage surface covered by corrosion after 504 hours salt spray test (%)	Visible changes after exposure to Danish weather for 12 months	Rate of corrosion by oxygen consumption after 70 days ($\mu\text{m year}^{-1}$)
None (bare panel)		100	corroded	130
Corroheat 4010	97/40	0	very discoloured	2.7
Cosmoloid H80	85/90	0	corrosion at edges	<0.1
Dinitrol Car/4941	100/50	0	loss of gloss. two rust spots	0.7
Frigilene	100/95	50	evenly corroded	0.1
Incralac	90/90	8	spots of corrosion	<0.1
LPS3	40/100	0	darkened	0.1
Paraloid B72	86/40	8	unevenly corroded	0.2
Paraloid B72 with 1% perfluorodecyl iodide (PI)	95/40	50	unevenly corroded	0.4
Poligen ES91009	100/100	50	discrete spots of corrosion	16.6
Renaissance wax	98/100	50	corroded	1.9
Rustilo 2000	100/100	8	evenly corroded	-
Rustilo 3000	100/100	1	loss of gloss	0.4
Ship-2-shore Industrial	liquid-unable to measure adhesion	50	very corroded	1.9
SP400	95/95	0	uneven appearance	0.2
Tectyl 506 rust preventative	100/100	0.5	discoloured	1.5
Tectyl Glashelder/Klar spray	100/100	50	30% surface corroded or discoloured	1.5
Tromm III	99/85	50	50% spots of corrosion	3.5
VpCI-386 acrylic primer/topcoat	100/100	1	20% spots of corrosion	0.1

Corroheat 4010

- ✓ good resistance to corrosion
- ✓ good adhesion to metal
- X highly discoloured after ageing

VPCI-386 ***

- ✓ transparent and high gloss
- ✓ readily removable with solvent

Conclusions

- selection of protective coatings from literature alone is a minefield – coatings are rarely compared on an equal basis
- oxygen consumption is a good predictor of protection from corrosion while adhesion tests are poor predictors
- evaluation by both physical and chemical/electrochemical techniques combined with salt spray and real time exposure suggests that wax-based coatings were more resistant to water, UV light and salt than acrylic-based
- selection of coatings is a compromise but any coating is better protection than no coating
- reference coatings should either be appropriate or absent